

Sustainability Report

What will you find?

Who we are

**What we
achieved**

**Methods we
used**

**Our
commitment
with the SDG
Goals**

Future goals

Who we are

This sustainability Report was created by the Colonia Avellaneda municipality. From this year we assumed the commitment to measure and evaluate our development throughout Sustainability Reports. Our main goal is to self-assess our projects and move forward to the continuous improvement. We took the decision to implement this tool because we understand that our citizens deserve a trustworthy and transparent information source about the sustainable management that is being implemented in the municipal government.

The modernization of Colonia Avellaneda aims at inclusion, equality and an improvement in the quality of life of the citizens. In this direction, it is not just necessary to generate the data base, but also to communicate them and promote a real access to it.

Colonia Avellaneda

The municipality of Colonia Avellaneda belongs to the Paraná district in Entre Ríos province, the central region from the country. Geographically belongs to the Mesopotamia and politically integrates the center Region, along with Córdoba and Santa Fé provinces.

Our mission

Inform and raise awareness in the community about the importance of source separation, at the same time that we provide professional development opportunities to women working in informal conditions, allowing them to become positive changemakers in their communities. Throughout education, community engagement and the implementation of sustainable practices, we aspire to build a greener and fairer future for everyone.

The GIIRSU System

Our main tool to achieve a change in our society is the GIIRSU System, being inclusion and formalization of urban recuperators one of the main objectives of this new model.

Identified stakeholders

For us is important to link up with stakeholders to participate in planning and decision-making as it allows us to design democratic and comprehensive policies that protect the interests of those affected by our decisions. This allows us to contemplate the satisfaction of common interests and incorporate their demands on the public policy.

Inner Groups

- Collaborators
- Secretary and municipality areas

External Groups

- Urban recuperators
- Neighbors from “Los Zorzales”
- Citizens in general
- National and Provincial Government
- Work Cooperatives

3-2, 3-3

What we achieved

Our performance in one image

Last year we achieved the inclusion of thousand of women, giving them a more dignifying job which also generates a positive impact in our municipality.

Our impact in numbers

3084

Censed people in Colonia Avellaneda

Of these, 103 were identified as urban recuperators and 45 of them were women. Thanks to the census we could know who they were and under what conditions they worked.

We provided formation courses which trained academically this women so they can pass on their knowledge to the society

We recruited the registered women, offered them a better, dignified and formal job opportunity. These were formed from two courses: Environmental Promoter Course and Trainers and Multipliers Course.

45

Women professionally formed

300

Awareness-raised Families

Based on our Communication Plan, by our environmental promoters.

All the previous and acquired knowledge of our promoters was transmitted to the families of the locality, creating awareness about the key role they play in source separation.

Which methods did we use?

Key milestones in our journey

Environmental Diagnosis: This tool enabled us to determine the current state of the study area, thus identifying what was the problem we were facing. It allowed us to visualize how landfills and the use of streams as open sewers caused impacts on the environment.

SWOT: It allowed identifying the strengths and weaknesses (internal environment) of the team with which we had, analyzing its resources and capabilities, as well as a list of threats and opportunities that is identified with the analysis of its environment (external environment).

Environmental Study: We identified the main impacts, caused by lack of proper waste management and how this generated impacts. Not just in the environment but also in the society itself. From the impacts we propose a solution with our enhancement project.

Enhancement Project: We proposed an enhancement project, focusing mainly in the social factor. Starting with the formalization of the urban recuperators, specifically the women section. Our purpose is to enable them to access to a better life quality and a dignified job at same time that we generate a positive impact on the environment, by educating and creating self awareness to the citizens from the municipality about the proper source separation, being this a fundamental stage on the correct, comprehensive and inclusive management of urban solid waste.

203-1, 203-2, 401-2, 403- 6, 404-2, 405-2, 406-1, 413-1

Our compromise with the SDGs

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a set of 17 social, economic, environmental and political goals agreed by global multilevel actors. These represent the challenge the world faces by 2030 to substantially improve people's lives and the environment through different actions. The 2030 Agenda is the name given to the set of objectives and their respective goals as a framework for different organizations.

As a municipality, we are also committed on meeting these objectives. Our management approach is based on the following ones:

Over the past year, our project helped a significant group of women to find decent employment, ending their poverty and improving their life quality.

We achieved an improvement in the quality of health of residents living in areas near the dump and people working in direct contact with garbage, improving their hygiene and safety.

Education and training was a key step in lifting women out of poverty by providing them with decent work. Training courses and spaces were funded and provided free of charge by the municipality

We approach the first policy with a gender perspective for women waste collectors, valuing their knowledge and experiences in issues related to waste separation and recycling, enhancing their capacities with training programs for them.

Our project allowed local women working in precarious conditions, where their health was at stake and their income was barely enough to survive to access decent work, where their abilities are valued, help them to progress and thus improve their quality of life.

We do this by providing more decent jobs, investing in education and skills development. We provide support to the most vulnerable marginalized groups formed by the municipal urban recuperators.

Future Goals

What we achieved this year was a cultural change in the notion that the Colonia Avellaneda neighbors have about the MSW throughout the implementation of the first stage of the GIIRSU: the promotion stage. We still have a long way to go, with the final objective of addressing all the stages of the plan:

PROMOCIÓN	RECOLECCIÓN PUERTA A PUERTA	TRANSPORTE	ACONDICIONAMIENTO	COMERCIALIZACIÓN
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotoras ambientales • Programas: • Puerta a puerta • Grandes generadores • Instituciones públicas • Puntos verdes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modalidades: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carros a pie • Carros a caballo • Moto-vehículos • Otros vehículos • Armado de RUTAS DE RECOLECCIÓN 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Modalidades: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flota específica • Aprovechar vehículos disponibles del Municipio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Galpón • Maquinaria: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Balanza • Enfardadora • Autoelevador 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VENTA COLECTIVA • DIRECTO A LA INDUSTRIA • TRANSPARENCIA EN LAS OPERACIONES

Promotion:

- Environmental promoters
- Door to Door pick up
- Big generators identification
- Public institutions
- Recycling points

Door to Door pick up:

- Walked wagons
- Horse traction
- Moto-vehicles
- Another type of vehicles

Transportation:

- Specific Fleet
- Take advantage of municipality owned vehicles

Conditioning:

- Warehouse
- Machinery
- Scale Baler
- machine
- Forklift

Commercialization:

- Crowdsale
- Straight to industries
- Transparent operations

We have been through this first stage successfully, working as a team and creating real changes in the community.